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ОСОБЕННОСТИ РЕМОДЕЛИРОВАНИЯ СЕРДЦА У БОЛЬНЫХ С ХРОНИЧЕСКОЙ СЕРДЕЧНОЙ НЕДОСТАТОЧНОСТЬЮ НА ФОНЕ ПОСТИНФАРКТНОГО МИОКАРДИОСКЛЕРОЗА И ДИЛАТАЦИОННОЙ КАРДИОМИОПАТИИ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Изучить особенности ремоделирования сердца у пациентов с дилатационной кардиомиопатией (ДКМП) и постинфарктным кардиосклерозом (ПИКС), которые могут быть использованы для дифференциальной диагностики этих заболеваний.

Были обследованы 32 пациента с ДКМП (27 мужчин и 5 женщин; возраст $43,1 \pm 2,3$ года) и 62 пациента с ПИКС (все мужчины, возраст $56,4 \pm 1,1$ года) с признаками хронической сердечной недостаточности (ХСН). Диагноз ДКМП был установлен на основании комплексного клинико-инструментального обследования, которое также включало коронарографию. У 19 пациентов диагноз ДКМП был подтвержден результатами патологоанатомического обследования. Диагноз ПИКС был установлен при наличии документально подтвержденного инфаркта миокарда в анамнезе, обнаружении признаков очагового повреждения миокарда на ЭКГ и, при эхокардиографическом исследовании, нарушений локальной сократимости в 2 или более сегментах. Всем пациентам и 14 здоровым лицам было проведено эхокардиографическое исследование.

Ключевые слова: постинфарктный кардиосклероз, хроническая сердечная недостаточность, ремоделирование сердца.

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FEATURES OF HEART REMODELING IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC HEART FAILURE DUE TO POST-INFARCTION MYOCARDIOSCLEROSIS AND DILATED CARDIOMYOPATHY

ANNOTATION

To study the features of cardiac remodelling in patients with dilated cardiomyopathy (DCMP) and postinfarction cardiosclerosis (PICC), which can be used for differential diagnosis of these diseases.

We examined 32 patients with DCMP (27 men and 5 women; age 43.1 ± 2.3 years) and 62 patients with PICC (all men, age 56.4 ± 1.1 years) with signs of chronic heart failure (CHF). The diagnosis of DCMP was established on the basis of a comprehensive clinical and instrumental examination, which also included coronarography. In 19 patients the diagnosis of DCMP was confirmed by the results of pathological examination. The diagnosis of PICC was established in the presence of a documented history of myocardial infarction, evidence of focal myocardial damage on ECG and, on echocardiographic examination, local contractility abnormalities in 2 or more segments. All patients and 14 healthy individuals underwent echocardiographic study.

Keywords: postinfarction cardiosclerosis, chronic heart failure, cardiac remodelling. Relevance.

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INFARKTDAN KEYINGI MIYOKARDIYOSKLEROZ VA DILATATSION KARDIYOMIYOPATIYA FONIDA SURUNKALI YURAK ETISHMOVCHILIGI BO'LGAN BEMORLARDA YURAKNI QAYTA QURISH XUSUSIYATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu kasalliklarning differentsial diagnostikasi uchun ishlatilishi mumkin bo'lgan dilyatatsion kardiomyopatiya va infarktdan keying kardioklerozi (IKK) bilan og'riqan bemorlarda yurakni qayta qurish xususiyatlarini o'rganish.

Biz surunkali yurak etishmovchiligi (SYuE) belgilari bo'lgan 32 nafar dilyatatsion kardiomyopatiya (27 erkak va 5 ayol; yoshi $43,1 \pm 2,3$ yil) va IKK bilan kasallangan 62 bemorni (barcha erkaklar, $56,4 \pm 1,1$ yosh) tekshirdik. Dilyatatsion kardiomyopatiya diagnostikasi keng qamrovli klinik va instrumental tekshiruv asosida o'rnatildi, unga koronar angiografiya ham kiradi. 19 bemorda dilyatatsion kardiomyopatiya tashxisi patologik tekshiruv natijalari bilan tasdiqlangan. IKK diagnostikasi miokard infarktining hujjatlashtirilgan tarixi, EKGda miokardning o'choqli shikastlanishi belgilarini aniqlash va ekokardiografik tekshiruvda 2 yoki undan ortiq segmentlarda mahalliy kontraktillikning buzilishi bilan belgilanadi. Barcha bemorlar va 14 nafar sog'lom odam ekokardiografik tekshiruvdan o'tkazildi.

Kalit so'zlar: infarktdan keyingi kardioklerozi, surunkali yurak etishmovchiligi, yurakni qayta qurish.

The main link in the pathogenesis of chronic heart failure (CHF) is cardiac remodelling, the essence of which, at least at the initial stages of heart failure development, cannot be characterised by signs of primary

myocardial damage. In this regard, it is of interest to study the patterns of ventricular remodelling.

Progression of CHF in patients with dilated cardiomyopathy (DCMP) and postinfarction myocardiosclerosis (PICS). DCMP is characterised by diffuse myocardial damage to both ventricles, while PICS is characterised by focal myocardial damage to the left ventricle. Echocardiography does not always allow us to distinguish cardiac dilatation from diffuse or focal myocardial lesions; therefore, identifying new differential diagnostic criteria for dilated cardiomyopathy and postinfarction myocardiosclerosis is important.

Objective. In this study, the aim was to identify features of cardiac remodelling in patients with DCMP and PICS that can be used for the differential diagnosis of these diseases.

Materials and Methods. We examined 32 patients with DCMP (27 men and 5 women, mean age 43.1 ± 2.3 years) and 62 patients with signs of CHF (all men, mean age 56.4 ± 1.1 years). The diagnosis of DCMP was made on the basis of complex clinical and instrumental examinations, including angiography. In 19 patients, the diagnosis of DCMP was confirmed pathologically.

Research. The diagnosis of PICS was based on confirmed myocardial infarction, ECG signs of focal myocardial damage and echocardiographic data (weakening of focal contraction in 2 or more segments). The patients were divided into six groups according to the diagnosis and stage of CHF. The actual control group consisted of 14 people. Healthy men (mean age 46.6 ± 1.6 years) were included. On echocardiographic examination in the four-chamber position (HP Sonos 2000, 3.5 MHz transducer), systolic BP was measured. The diastolic length of the left ventricle (LVSD and LVDD) and right ventricle (RVDV and RVDD) corresponds to the distance from the end of the respective ventricle to the centre of the annulus during systole and diastole, respectively. The systolic and diastolic left ventricular velocities (SLV and LVV), which are equal to the maximum distance between the interventricular septum and the left ventricular free wall during the corresponding phase of the cardiac cycle, were also measured. Systolic and diastolic left ventricular sphericity indices (LV Sis and LV Dis) were calculated as the ratio of left ventricular width to length during systole and diastole, respectively. The modified Simpson formula determined left ventricular end-diastolic (LVED) and end-systolic (LVES) volumes. Right ventricular end-diastolic (RVED) and right ventricular end-systolic volume (RVESV) were calculated as the difference between the total volume of both chambers and the combined volume of the left ventricular cavity and interventricular septum during the corresponding phase of the cardiac cycle [8]. For comparative assessment of the structural state of the left and right ventricles, the LVEF/SSV, LVEF/SSV, LVEF/SSV and LVEF/SSV ratios were calculated.

Mean values (M) and representativeness errors (m) were calculated for all considered indicators. The significance of differences between groups was evaluated using Student's t-criterion for unrelated variants.

Results. The data in Table 1 show that in patients with stage I, IIA or IIB DCMP and CHF, the mean EDV exceeded that of the control group by 51, 86 and 104%, respectively, and that the mean EDV was 19, 37 and 63%, respectively. In other words, the progression of CHF in patients with DCMP is associated with an increase in the end-diastolic volume of both the left and right ventricles, but left ventricular dilatation develops faster than right ventricular dilatation does. Consequently, at each stage of CHF, the EDV/EDV ratio is significantly greater in DCMP patients (by 28-41%) than in healthy individuals.

The increase in the LVEDV during the progression of CHF in patients with PICS occurs at the same rate as that in patients with DCMP. In stages I, IIA and IIB of CHF, the mean EDVs in patients with PICS exceeded the control values by 51, 82 and 117%, respectively. However, the LVEDV in stage I and IIA PICS patients with CHF practically does not differ from that in healthy individuals, and only at stage IIB does it increase 1.5 times in comparison with that in the control group. Thus, the ratio of LVEDV/RVEDV in PICS patients at any stage of CHF is 46-71% greater than that in healthy individuals and 14-21% greater than that in DCMP patients.

In DCMP patients, the mean LVESV and RVESV at stage I CHF were 2.3 and 2.1 times greater than those in the control group, respectively; at stage IIA, 3.5 and 2.5 times greater; and at stage IIB, 3.9 times greater than and 4.2 times greater than those in the control group.

In connection with the almost proportional increase in the LVESV and RVESV during the progression of CHF in DCMP patients, the ratio of these indices remained almost unchanged and significant.

In patients with PICS, the mean CSFOLs in stages I, IIA and IIB of CHF exceeded those in the control group by 2, 3 and 4 times, respectively. Moreover, the average PICSs in stages I and IIA of CHF patients practically does not differ from that in healthy individuals, and in stage IIB, the average PICS increases more than threefold fold. Accordingly, the ratio of LVESV/RVESV in patients with PICS stage I and IIA CHF is on average 2.1-2.9 times greater than that in healthy individuals and in patients with DCMP. However, in stage IIB CHF patients, the LSV/SVL ratio in patients with PICS decreases sharply and no longer differs from the LSV/SVL ratio in healthy individuals and patients with DCMP.

In patients with PICS, as in patients with DCMP, an increase in left ventricular dilatation is accompanied by an increase in diastolic and especially systolic sphericity indices. Moreover, the mean LVEDV and LVESV at each stage of CHF in patients with DCMP were slightly greater than those in patients with PICS, although these differences reached statistical significance only for the LVEDV at stage I of CHF.

In contrast to patients with DCMP, in patients with PICS, the progression of CHF is accompanied by a steady increase in DDLV. The average values of this index in stage I, IIA and IIB PICS patients with CHF exceeded those in healthy individuals by 8, 14 and 17%, respectively. At the same time, LREF also increases, but this increase starts from a much lower value than that in the control group. The average DDRVs in stage I, IIA and IIB PICS patients with CHF were 91, 94 and 99%, respectively, of the index of healthy individuals. The DDLV/DDRv ratio does not change during the progression of CHF in patients with PICS but is significantly (by 23-27%) greater than that in patients with DCMP.

Among CHF patients with DCMP in stages I, IIA and IIB, the DCMP exceeds that in healthy individuals by 19%, 20% and 30%, respectively, and the SDLV exceeds that in patients with DCMP in stages 21, 24% and 28%, respectively. The ratio of SDLV/SDRV during the progression of CHF remains stable and very close to that in healthy subjects. The increase in the SDIj during the progression of CCN in patients with PICS was more pronounced than that in patients with DCMP. At stages I, IIA and IIB of CHF, the average value of SDLV in these patients exceeded that in the control group by 25, 36 and 41%, respectively. The ratio of SDLV/SDRV during the progression of CHF in these patients remains adequately stable and is significantly greater (by 38-44%) than that in DCMP patients.

Discussion. The study showed that at stage I of CHF, that is, in the absence of clinical signs of stasis of the large and small circulatory circle under conditions of physical rest, there was a reliable and statistically significant increase in the number of examined patients compared with healthy people with LVEDV and an even more significant increase in the LVESV. The progression of CHF in both groups of patients was accompanied by a further increase in left ventricular volume both in systole and diastole. However, in patients with stage I and IIA CHF, the left ventricular length practically does not change and only slightly increases in stage IIB. A pronounced increase in left ventricular volume with a slight increase in length indicates that the left ventricle changes its spatial geometry and becomes more spherical. It can be assumed that this type of left ventricular remodelling in DCMP patients is associated with the diffuse nature of myocardial damage. In focal left ventricular lesions, the intact myocardium preserves the elliptical shape of the left ventricle so that its dilatation is accompanied by an increase not only in volume but also in length.

In our opinion, the observed discrepancy is because the sphericity index, despite its name, does not reflect the geometric characteristics of the cavity in the left ventricle well but rather reflects the characteristics of its two-dimensional projection on the secant plane in the four-chamber position. Formally, the sphericity index can also be calculated for the right ventricle, but due to its special "geometry", this index reflects the features of the two-dimensional projection of the right ventricle onto the secant plane in the four-chamber position. of the right ventricle will in no way will not reflect the characteristics of its three-dimensional structure.

It is clear that right ventricular remodelling during the progression of CHF should be significantly different between patients with DCM and those with PICS. In the first case, both ventricles of the heart are affected simultaneously; in the second case, as a rule, only the left ventricle is affected at first, and only after its decompensation are the right ventricles involved in the pathological process.

In fact, as the results of this study have shown, right ventricular remodelling in patients with DCM parallels left ventricular remodelling and does not fundamentally differ from it. As the severity of CHF increases, the right ventricular volume increases significantly, and the length increases modestly. Given the geometry of the right ventricle, it would be incorrect to use the term "sphericity" in relation to its cavity, but it can be said that due to the advantage of a significant increase in the transverse dimensions of the right ventricle, the free wall and the heart as a whole acquire a spherical shape. It is more difficult to explain another result of this study, which showed that the diastolic and especially systolic length of the right ventricle in patients with stage I CHF PICS is significantly and reliably shorter than in healthy individuals. In our opinion, this phenomenon should be explained by the geometry of the right ventricle, which can be represented as a pocket outside the left ventricle. Dilation of the left ventricle is accompanied by an increase in the area covered by the right ventricle and "pulling" of the free wall toward the interventricular septum, especially in the vertebral region. In the basal regions, this effect is prevented by fixation of the free wall of the right ventricle on the fibrous ring. Before

discussing the results of the study regarding their practical significance, we should emphasise the limited possibilities of echocardiographic studies in the differential diagnosis of dilated and ischaemic cardiomyopathies [9]. At present, the most important area of study is known to be akinesia, which can occur in the DCM due to an uneven decrease in myocardial contractility [10] and is absent from ischaemic myocardial damage accompanied by a pronounced decrease in total systolic function.

Conclusions. In stage I CHF patients with PICS, there is a moderate increase in the volume and length of the left ventricular cavity compared to healthy individuals. The right ventricular volume was not increased, but the length of the right ventricle was significantly less than that in healthy individuals. In patients with DCM, there is an increase in the volume and length of both ventricles of the heart. In stage IIA CHF patients, compared to those in stage I, the volume and length of lesions in patients with PICS are greater, while in patients with DCM, only the volume of the left ventricle is greater. Neither the right ventricular volume nor the length did not change in patients with DCM or patients with PICS. In stage IIB CHF patients, the volume and length of both ventricles of the heart increase in both patients with PICS and patients with DCM. At any stage of CHF, the ratio of left ventricle length to right ventricle length in patients with PICS is significantly greater than that in patients with DCM, which creates prerequisites for the use of this index in differential diagnostics of ischaemic and nonischaemic dilatation of the heart.

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